

Table 1. Yields of HKR228 and Basmati 370 in varietal trials at Kaul and Karnal, Haryana, India.

Year	Location	Yield (t/ha)		LSD (0.05)	CV (%)
		HKR228	Basmati 370		
1985	Kaul	4.9	3.5	0.5	6.8
	Karnal	4.7	2.9	1.2	14.8
1986	Kaul	5.2	3.0	0.3	4.0
	Karnal	5.5	4.8	0.7	6.4
1987	Kaul	6.1	4.3	0.8	6.8
1988	Kaul	4.8	3.5	0.7	8.0
1989	Kaul	5.1	3.6	0.2	2.87
	Karnal	5.5	3.4	0.4	4.02
1990	Kaul	2.8	1.1	0.1	3.20
	Karnal	4.9	2.8	0.6	7.57
Mean		4.95	3.29		

that of Basmati 370. Kernel elongation after cooking is 1.76, with 25.41% amylose content.

HKR228 is resistant to blast, stem rot, and whitebacked planthopper (Table 2).

Integrated germplasm improvement—rainfed

Neeraja, a high-yielding rice variety for poorly drained rainfed fields in Kerala

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In Kerala, rainfed rice is cultivated on 320,000 ha during the wet season (Apr-May to Sep-Oct). Flooding is a major problem during early crop growth.

We screened 500 entries under poorly drained conditions. After transplanting, the experimental field was flooded to 50 cm for 2 wk.

Promising cultivars were tested for yield at Pattambi and in farmers' fields.

Bangladesh line BR51315-4 was most promising, and has been released as Neeraja (Ptb 47).

Neeraja is semitall (110-120 cm), nonlodging, with 140-d duration (see table). Its grain is white and slender. Yields are 4-5 t/ha under average management (40-9-17 kg NPK/ha). Straw yields

Performance of Neeraja in station and adaptive trials.

Culture or variety	Parentage	Plant height (cm)	Tillers (no./plant)	Duration (d)		Grain yield (tha)		Mean grain yield (t/ha) from adaptive trials
				Main crop	Ratoon crop	Main crop	Ratoon crop	
Neeraja (BR51-315-4)	IR20/Pankaj	115	8	140	55	3.9	1.6	4.9
BR52-96-3	IR20/IR5	108	7	145	55	3.5	1.4	4.4
Ptb 1	Local check	137	7	140	55	1.5	—	2.7
LSD (0.05)						0.7		

Table 2. Characteristics of HKR228 and Basmati 370.

Character	HKR228	Basmati 370
Days to maturity	143	144
Plant height (cm)	116	144
Panicles (no./m ²)	251	269
Grains (no./m ²)	131	89
1 000-grain weight (g)	19.0	21.5
Brown rice (%)	77.8	73.3
Milled rice (%)	72.5	65.0
Kernel length (mm)	7.06	6.70
Kernel breadth (mm)	1.58	1.62
L/B ratio	4.47	4.13
Kernel length after cooking (mm)	12.43	13.54
Kernel elongation ratio	1.76	2.02
Alkali value	6.50	5.05
Amylose content (R)	25.41	19.84
Grain type	Long slender	Long slender
Leaf blast resistance (0-9 scale)	3.0	7.0
Stem rot resistance (0-5 scale)	2.25	2.25
Bacterial leaf blight resistance (0-9 scale)	8.0	9.0
Whitebacked planthopper resistance (0-9 scale)	1.0	0.0

are 8-10 t/ha. Ratoon yields average 1.5 t/ha within 50-55 d. It is moderately resistant to blast and sheath blight.

Neeraja is recommended for poorly drained fields and double-cropped wetlands. □

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Soil microbiology

Response of blue-green algae (BGA) in wetland rice culture in Himachal Pradesh, India

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We studied during wet season 1990 the effect on rice of BGA inoculation with different levels of applied N. Experimental soil was sandy loam, with pH 7.2, medium organic C (0.60%) and available N (110 kg/ha), and low available P (3.5 kg/ha).

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications; plot size was 5 × 4.75 m.

Thirty-day-old seedlings of IR579 were transplanted 7 Jul 1990. Dry soil-based BGA inoculum was broadcast 10 d after transplanting. The crop was harvested 10 Oct.

A mother culture of BGA procured from the National Facility for Blue-Green Algae Collections, Indian Agricultural Research Institute, at New Delhi was multiplied in the field during June. Ten

kilograms of loamy soil mixed with 200 g single superphosphate was spread on a 15- × 7.5- × 22.5-cm galvanized iron tray flooded to 7.5 cm, and 250 g mother culture broadcast. A thick mat of BGA formed in about 10 d.

The water was allowed to evaporate and the dry BGA flakes with some soil were collected and ground for inoculum.

Inoculated plots produced a luxuriant growth of BGA, about 4 kg fresh weight/m². No microscopic observations were made because of the lack of facilities. The dominant algae biomass resembled *Anabaena* morphologically. A BGA bloom during maximum tillering continued up to panicle initiation, then gradually diminished.

Effect of inoculating BGA with and without applied N on irrigated rice yields. Himachal Pradesh, India, 1990 wet season.

Treatment (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Plant height (cm) at harvest	Panicle length (cm) at harvest	Grain number (no./panicle) at harvest
BGA ₀ N ₀	2.1	5.2	80.0	18.3	131
BGA ₀ N ₃₀	2.4	6.4	80.5	19.4	147
BGA ₀ N ₆₀	2.6	7.7	82.9	20.0	150
BGA ₀ N ₉₀	2.9	8.6	84.0	20.0	151
BGA ₁₀ N ₀	2.5	6.2	81.0	20.4	159
BGA ₁₀ N ₃₀	3.0	6.6	81.0	19.5	168
BGA ₁₀ N ₆₀	3.1	8.1	81.5	21.0	174
BGA ₁₀ N ₉₀	3.5	9.0	82.5	21.3	177
LSD (0.05)					
BGA	0.4				
N	0.1	0.4			
BGA×N	0.2	0.6			

Grain and straw yields were highest with 10 kg BGA + 90 kg N/ha (see table). Grain yields, but not straw yields, were

influenced significantly by BGA. Nearly half a ton extra grain was obtained from BGA application. □

Integrated fertilizer management

Long-range effect of continuous cropping and fertilizer application on yield stability of Wet Season (ws) rice

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We began a long-range fertilizer experiment in 1977 (Apr-Sep) WS. Treatments included three N levels, three P levels, and two K levels, with a no-treatment control.

The experimental area was double-cropped wetland with sandy clay loam soil (riverine alluvium deposited over laterite soil), 71% sand, and 5% silt.

Initial soil analysis on composite samples from the top 20 cm layer showed pH 5.2; EC 0.25 dS/m; 0.72% organic C; and 156, 31, 178 kg available N, P, K/ha. The experimental layout was a partially confounded randomized block design with four replications. Jaya was the test variety.

Grain yields averaged over 14 WSs in continuous WS cropping experiment. Kerala, India, 1977-91.

Fertilizer	Grain yield (t/ha)					
	No P	17.6 kg P/ha	35 kg P/ha	NoK	33 kg K/ha	Mean(N)
40 kg N/ha	3.4	3.9	3.9	3.8	3.7	3.8
80 kg N/ha	3.8	4.2	4.3	4.2	4.0	4.1
120 kg N/ha	3.9	4.4	4.5	4.2	4.3	4.3
Mean (P & K)	3.7	4.2	4.2	4.1	4.0	
No K	3.8	4.2	4.3			
33 kg K/ha	3.7	4.1	4.2			
LSD N and P	0.2					

N level significantly affected yields for 9 yr (see table). P level significantly affected yields for the last 10 yr. The delayed response to P may be due to a residual effect. No response to potash occurred, perhaps because of the high soil K content. With no fertilizer, yields varied from 3.7 t/ha in 1977 to 2.7 t/ha in 1990. □

Crop management

Effect of tillage practices on deepwater rice (DWR) yield and return

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In DWR areas, land preparation is done when water recedes. We studied the effect of six different tillage practices in a randomized block design with four replications in 1988 and 1989 wet seasons (Apr-Dec).

Soil at the experimental site was clay loam (Aridisol) with pH 8.2, 0.52% organic C, 11 kg available P, 248 kg K/ha.

Rice variety Jalmagna was direct seeded in rows 25 cm apart on 20 Apr

1988 and 25 Apr 1989. Plot size was 90 m². Basal fertilizer was 40 kg N, 8.8 kg P/ha. Water started to rise in Jul, reaching a maximum 240 cm in Aug 1988 and 210 cm in Sep 1989.

Yields differed significantly both years (see table). Highest grain yield, net return, and benefit:cost ratio were with one moldboard plowing plus two plowings by country plow, with planking after each plowing. □